

SPIRITUALITY AND ASTROLOGY

M. Murugarajan* & Dr. G. Subramanian**

* Research Scholar, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Research Supervisor, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Our saints have given more explanation about soul. Each planet donotes a particular god to worship. Trine darma 1/5/9 bhavas shows one's spiritual achievement. Sun, Jupiter, Saturn and Kethu are very important planets to achieve spirituality. There are three types of Karma. There are Sanchitha karma. Proptha Karma and Agaamiya Karma. Some planetary combinations make one to shine in spiritual world.

Key Words: Saints, Soul, Planets, Particular God, 1/5/9, Sun, Jupiter, Saturn, Kethu, 3 Karma, Sanchitha Karma, Praptha Karma, Agaamiya Karma, Horoscope, Shine, Spirituality

Introduction:

Spirituality and astrology are never separated. Both of them help us to reach the eternal supreme god. The final moto of human life is to reach the heaven or paradise.

Spirituality According to Swami Vivekananda:

Takeup one idea. Make that one idea your life. Dream of it, think of it, live on that idea let the brain, the body, muscels, nerves, every part of your body be full of that idea, and just leave every other idea alone. This is the way to success.

Spirituality According to Jaggi Vasudev (ISHA YOGA):

Spirituality is the science to understand the soul.

Spirituality According to Pandit Poojyam Sri Ravishankar:

He is the founder of Art of living. He says that spirituality helps to know the soul. But you would loss yourself to know the soul.

Spirituality According to Buddha:

Buddha's teaching are known as dharma. He taught that wisdom, kindness, patience, generosity and compassion were important virtues.

Spirituality According to Ramana Maharishi:

The father of yoga marga. Ramana Maharishi was born at Tiruchuli near Aruppukkottai. He told that the answer for the question who am I is the way to reach god. One should do self-experiment. We are not bodies. We are not thoughts. We are not feelings we are not minds. Myself is the consciousness.

Spirituality According to Vedathri Maharishi:

He was the founder of Arivu Thirukovil (Wisdom Temple). It's headquarters is in Azhiyar near Pollachi. He said that feeling the soul is our goal.

Spirituality Related Bhavas in Horoscope:

Dharma triangle 1/5/9 and 12 th bhavas indicates one's spiritual level.

First Bhava: It show's one's characters, habits and natural qualities. If this bhava is aspected by Jupiter the native will shine in spiritual world.

Fifth Bhava: It is called as Poorva punya sthana. It indicates our previous janma karma. It also indicates the family diety. If we had done good karma in our previous janma, now our life is blissful. If we had done bad karma in our previous janma, now our life is sorrowful.

Nineth Bhava: It is called as packia sthana. If the nineth Lord stays in his own house or exhaltation the native build temples and do kumbabisegam. God's grace always with them.

Twelveth Bhava: It is called as moksha sthama. It gives one a way to reach the heaven or paradise. If kethu conjunctions with twelveth bhava, the native will reach the heaven easily. There is no next janma to born.

Planets and Prayers:

S.No	Planets	Connecting god
1	Sun	Lord Shiva
2	Moon	Lord Parvathi
3	Mars	Lord Muruga
4	Mercury	Lord Vishnu
5	Jupiter	Jeeva Samathi
6	Venus	Lord Ambika
7	Saturn	Lord Ayyappa
8	Rahu	Lord Kaliyamman
9	Kethu	Lord Vinayaga

Spiritual Planets:

There are four planets connected with Spirituality. They are Sun, Saturn, Jupiter and Kethu.

- Sun: Sun is the Athama karagan. He is the reason for earth creation. He gives us Soul. He gets first place in astrology.
- Saturn: Saturn is the Karma Karaga. According to our good karma or bad karma he will act as a judge So, he gets exhaltation in Libra. It's symbol is scale.
- Jupiter: Jupiter seeing planets and bhavaas are developed. Jupiter is the high positive vibrational planet. It helps one to shine in spriritual world.
- Kethu: Kethu is called as wisdom planet. If it stands in twelveth bhava, surely there is no next birth/ directly the native will reach the heaven or paradise.

Three types of Karma:

- Sanchitha Karma: These are the accumulated works and actions that you have completed in the past. These cannot be charges but can only wait to come into fruition. This is the vast accumulation of karma that encompasses our countless past lifetimes. This comprises every action that you have ever made in your past and present lives.
- Prarabdha Karma: Prarabdha karma is that portion of the past karma that is responsible for the preson. These are the ripe and fructuous actions and reactions the things that you did in the past make you what you are today. It cannot be avoided or changed, but only exhausted by being experienced.
- Agami Karma: Agami Karma is the Karma we are creating for ourselves right here in the current moment. It is the action that we create and the choices we make right now, as we live this present life time. Saturn is the planet for agami karma.

Example Horoscope 1:

12	ASC KETHU	2	3
11	Rasi		4
10			SUN
JUPITER	8	RAHU	6

The above horoscope, Aries lagna Kethu in lagna, Sun in Leo his own house, Rahu in Libra, Jupiter in Sagittarius his own house, the native should be shine in spirituality. He builds many temples and always having simple, life. He gets name and fame easily.

Example Horoscope 2:

2	3	4	5
ASC	Rasi		6
SATURN KETHU			7
11	10	9	8

The above horoscope the native will go to heaven directly because of the conjunction of saturn and Kethu in twelveth bhava. He lives as a siddha or Yogi or Saint and spends his life in spiritual path.

Example Horoscope 3:

9	10	11	12
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8	Rasi		ASC JUPITER
SATURN			2
6	SUN	4	3

The above horoscope, the ninth Lord Jupiter exhaltated in lagna. Saturn and Jupiter aspected each other. Sun the athma Karaga. Stands in Poorva Punya sthana. Sun is aspected by Jupiter. So he dedicates his life for spirituality.

Example Horoscope 4:

6	SUN	8	9
SATURN KETHU			10
4			11
3	2	ASC JUPIER	12

The above horoscope, Satun and kethu in fifth bhava and aspected by Jupiter. The eleventh Lord Sun got exhaltation power. Saturn also stands its own house. So, the native do spiritaual service throught out his life

Example Horoscope 5:

4	JUPITER	6	7
3			8
2			9
ASC SUN	SATURN	11	10

The above horoscope the ninth Lord Sun in lagna and aspected by the lagna lord Jupiter. Saturn stands in Motcha Sthana, Twelveth bhava. So, the native build temple in his home.

Example Horoscope 6:

3	4	5	6
2			7
ASC KETHU			8
12	11	10	SATURN JUPITER

The above horoscope lagna Lord Saturn stands in nineth bhava with Jupiter gives Guru chandala yoga. So, he got detachment from family. Kethu in lagna also boost up him in Spirituality.

Conclusion:

Material life makes us do sins and negative karmas. But the spiritual life makes us do punya and good karmas. So, we must do only good karmas. It helps our children to live their life happily.

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